
THE ROAD AHEAD FOR INDIAN ECONOMY POST COVID-19

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ABSTRACT

The most recent GDP data for India has reported negative growth of 23.9% for the quarter ending June 2020. One may easily blame COVID-19 for this massive economic shock but do we understand the threat of COVID-19 in its entirety or how other factors played a role? The answer is NO. It is quite simple to review these numbers and make a prediction for the future, based on statistics, as all rating agencies typically do, but when it comes to India, the answer may be a bit different. Like all other countries, India is divided into the formal and informal sector. As per the NITI Aayog data from an Economic Survey for the year 2018-2019, 93 % of the total workforce in India originates from the informal sector. Indian GDP data does not include the informal economy but does include an estimate. This recent data of -23.9% GDP is the worst negative growth ever recorded in history for the country. The fact is, it could be a lot worse, as it does not include the backbone of the Indian economy i.e. the informal sector. This data does not include the most significant population in the Indian workforce. The informal sector consists of around 500 million people significantly more than the American population of 330 million people and does not address how this sector was impacted by COVID-19. The core of India's economy was simply overlooked. The present study highlights the road ahead for Indian economy in future years. The paper puts certain remedies to overcome the present situation.

Keywords: COVID 19, GDP, Indian economy, formal sector, informal sector.

INTRODUCTION

Indian economy suffered its nastiest slump on record in April-June, with the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) contracting by 23.9 % as the COVID-19 related lockdowns weighed on the already declining consumer demand and investment. The GDP contraction in the world's 5th largest economy compared with 3.1 % growth in the preceding January-March quarter and 5.2 % expansion in the same period a year back. This is the sharpest contraction since quarterly figures started being published in 1996 and worse than what was expected by most analysts.

REASONS FOR ECONOMIC TURBULENCE

Most of India and the world went into a severe lockdown in the April to June period. Most economic and business activity came to a halt. In May, 2020 India had announced a 266 billion dollars stimulus package i.e. free food to the weak and poor, jobs for migrant workers credit guarantees on bank loans and, relief to small businesses. But, that has not helped cushion the fall; the economy is still crawling out of the lockdown.

The blow from a virtual shutdown of a nation of 1.3 billion people has been so harsh that economists are struggling to forecast how long it will take to recover. With Asia's 3rd largest economy heading for its first full-year contraction in more than four decades — some say of as much as 5%, it may be a while yet before India can get back to its peaceful days of 8% plus growth. The lockdown is likely to see corporate India's revenues and profits fall, leading to a sharp jump in bad loans among lenders and crisis-ridden shadow banks, all of which would hurt capital formation and investment activity. Even consumers, whose spending has been fueled by loans and are a key driver of growth, are unlikely to take on more debt at a time when jobs are uncertain.

However, it was not just India's worst ever quarter. Some of the world's largest economies have not been able to bear the brunt of the pandemic. In the April to June, 2020 period the US economy contracted by 32.9 %. The United Kingdom by 20.4 per cent, Japan by 27.8 %.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present study has the following objectives:

- a) To highlight the reasons for slow growth of Indian economy;
- b) To analyze the road ahead for Indian economy;
- c) To present suggestions for the improvement of Indian economy.

ROAD AHEAD FOR INDIAN ECONOMY

The chief economic advisor Krishnamurthy Subramanian expects a recovery once India comes completely out of lockdown. But, he also expects the uncertainty to remain until the pandemic is completely brought under control. The path for Indian economy can be highlighted from the following points:

- ❖ India has finally lifted inter-state movement of vehicles. As goods and services move across the country freely — the Indian economy should begin its upward climb. But this will be a tough climb. India's woes won't end in a hurry. The economy is expected to contract by 6 percent in 2020.
- ❖ It is believed that a catch-up to the pre-crisis trend level of gross domestic product growth will not be possible in the next three fiscal years despite policy support.
- ❖ The median estimate in a Bloomberg's survey of economists is for a 1.9% contraction in GDP in the fiscal year through March 2021, and a rebound to 7.1% next year.
- ❖ While 7% expansion would be welcome in most places, that pace isn't enough to generate jobs for the 12-15 million Indians seeking employment every year. It also hurts Prime Minister's ambition to turn India into a \$5 trillion economy by 2025.
- ❖ Any rebound may be well short of the spurt seen after the global financial crisis more than a decade ago. India expanded at an average of 8.2% in the two fiscal years following the crisis, boosted by massive fiscal spending, monetary easing and a swift global recovery—all of which played a key role in ensuring a V-shaped recovery. To strengthen growth, policy makers have extended support in the form of credit guarantees and removed supply-side bottlenecks in various sectors. But direct cash transfers to citizens have been modest, and the central bank's sharp interest rate cuts and billions of dollars of liquidity have had very little impact on overall demand so far.
- ❖ Regarding the time taken by the countries to reach the pre-virus growth levels, the country-wise past recession experience suggests that the recovery in economic activity and the capital formation tends to be slow and it typically takes roughly five to 10 years for real economic activity to reach its former peak level.
- ❖ As per report by Care Ratings, even as the Indian economy gradually recovers from the impact of the nationwide lockdown, six sectors may have to wait for a long time to see the signs of revival. Hospitality & tourism, NBFCs, airport allied services, retail (excluding essential goods), real estate and seaports are the sectors that are likely to take more than a year to heal the wounds of COVID 19 pandemic. The report also listed few major roadblocks created by the lockdown, which are labour migration; sharp fall in revenue and profits; low capacity utilization; liquidity crisis and disruption in logistics.
- ❖ The COVID-19 pandemic has introduced a short-term contraction of demand and supply, sling with the structural shift resulting in a long-term impact on the industry. The impact of COVID-19 on India companies would be prolonged and accentuated for the small and mid-sized corporate sector and the financial services sector, the report added. However, efforts made by the Indian Government are expected to reduce some pain from the economy.
- ❖ The financial services sector including the Non Banking Finance Companies and banking sector are expected to take a long-term hit as they were already impacted by the sub-optimal Gross Domestic Product growth of the last two years, followed by the liquidity crisis. Adding to the woes, the option of moratorium and its extension is further expected to shoot up Non Performing Assets for the sector.
- ❖ There are several hurdles the economy will encounter:

- a) A fall in the value for the rupee against the dollar, reducing India’s dollar-denominated GDP.
 - b) A frequent state assembly election cycles, leading to populist policies, not necessarily sensible, reformist economic policies.
 - c) Stalled privatization of listed Public Sector Units (PSUs), robbing them off greater efficiencies.
 - d) Tepid export growth, worsening India’s trade deficit.
 - e) A lingering Covid-19 pandemic, stalling the resumption of full economic activity.
- Despite these caveats, the Indian economy will move forward haltingly but stubbornly.
- ❖ Modi’s entreaty to be “Vocal about Local” should be amended to “Vocal about Local and Global”. To achieve a \$6 trillion GDP by 2030, India needs to be not only self-reliant but make the world India-reliant.
 - ❖ The top priority is the financial sector. Bringing public sector banks under the exclusive regulation of RBI and reducing public ownership to less than 50% are necessary but not sufficient reforms, as the private sector scams at Yes Bank, IL&FS, etc. have shown.
 - a) So, strengthening the supervision of both banks and non-bank finance companies is key to cracking the non-performing assets problem.
 - b) Fiscal reforms should include a sharp reduction in tax concessions and exemptions, a policy reversal on discretionary ad hoc tariffs, elimination of non-merit subsidies, and a progressive shifting of central and state government expenditure towards education, health and physical infrastructure.
 - c) In the power sector, the core reform required is privatization of distribution. The experience of states like Delhi can serve as templates for others.
 - d) India needs to abolish regulations that dis-incentivize the growth of small and medium enterprises, such as the Factories Act. This is essential for rapid growth of employment in industry and services.
 - e) Public enterprise reform has proven intractable, but state-run firms should either win or wither in fair competition with private enterprises without repeated capital infusions at the cost of taxpayers.
 - f) In agriculture the key requirement is to reform the marketing system to narrow the huge margins between what consumers pay and farmers earn.
 - ❖ Apart from economic reforms, the quality of our governance institutions, the legislature, executive and judiciary, also impinge on economic performance. Strengthening these is essential to sustain high growth. Finally, reforms are to be seen as a process, not an event. Past experience in China, India and elsewhere suggests that it could take up to a decade for the process to work itself out and return us to a path of high growth.

GOOD SIGN FOR INDIAN ECONOMY

Now the lockdown is over and demand for products is on increasing trend. As per Bloomberg’s report, Indian economy has picked up the speed. And now festive season is about to come, so there is an expectation of increased demand and consumption.

Out of eight indicators of GDP, five indicators have shown an improvement which are mentioned herein below:

S. No.	Sectors	Particulars and Trends	
1	Improvement in commercial activities	Service sector is showing good sign of growth. The index of service sector is now increasing.	Index of service sector September, 2020: 49.8 August, 2020: 41.8 July, 2020: 34.2 April, 2020: 5.4 This shows great sign of improvement

2	Growth in manufacturing sector	Manufacturing sector is now showing increasing trend after five months of declining. Now PMI Index is showing an upward trend.	PMI Index September, 2020: 56.8 This is highest since the year 2012
3	Relief on the Export front	Export has also shown a sign of relief in the month of September, 2020	In September, 2020 exports increases by 6 percent as compared to last year. The export of Medicine, drugs and pharma, chemicals has led to increase in exports
4	Increase in Demand	Due to reduction in COVID cases, the demand for products increases.	In September, 2020 the sale of automobiles increase by 26.5 % as compared to last year.
5	Industrial Production on rise	Capital Goods Output which is an important index of demand in economy dropped by 15.8 % Now it is showing upward trend.	In August, 2020 industrial production dropped by 8 % and in July, 2020 dropped by 10.8 %.

STEPS TO GO AHEAD

It is absolutely uncertain, how long we will have to live with COVID. The post-corona economic recovery is going to be a herculean task for most of the countries including India. The present 'COVID period' has to be dealt with on a war-footing level. Economic activism and human safety have created a massive dilemma in all the countries. Yet a lot of innovation will have to be used with caution to support the down - trodden people. For Indian perspective, following remedies as immediate, short term and long term are presented herein below. The long-term remedies are strategic in nature. A brief account of these remedies is presented herein below:

Immediate Remedies:

Immediate remedies include the following:

- Create a 'national fund' to pay the unemployed for six months (50% of funds of temples, churches & mosques may be used)
- Offer 'cash credit' to SMEs @ 3% interest
- Introduce around 20% cut in the salaries of government officials, at least for the Corona period
- Engage youngsters to manage schools through double or triple shifts
- Create direct connect between farmers & consumer groups
- Offer special credit to Kiranawalas
- Give interest free cash loans to small farmers
- Levy 'COVID Cess' on profitable corporate
- Finance 'public health infrastructure' 100%
- Spend special budget on public transport
- Facilitate the movement, shelter & jobs of the migrant labour

Short - Term Remedies

Short-term remedies include the following:

- Raise cheaper funds from Japan to improve the health of public sector banks & scheduled banks
- Concentrate on those commodities, which can be 'import substitutes' for Chinese products
- Finance small & medium size non-banking finance companies (NBFCs) for their short term health

- Consolidate 'micro financing agencies' through mergers
- Arrange a complete value-chain of farmers, Kiranawalas & consumers
- Promote public health centres
- Arrange insurance for covering the revenue losses of MSMEs, farmers & unorganized labour

Long Term Strategic Remedies

Long – Term remedies include the following:

- Build-up National Calamity Fund (NCF)
- Create Farmers' Cooperative Confederation
- Create Kiranawalas' Cooperative Confederation
- 'Make In India', a high priority to replace China globally
- New Socio-Economic Alliances in the global market
- Skill & ethos-based free education to all types of backward communities
- Rebuilding of all public sector enterprises & banks, keeping common man at the centre of the economy.
- Create Consumers' Cooperative Confederation
- Design & build-up 'Cluster Civilization' to promote local economies
- Agriculture & agro-based industry to be the focus of local economies

CONCLUSION

It is especially important to understand the structure of the Indian economy if India is to even begin to aspire to becoming a \$5 trillion economy.

In light of this, the path of achieving the dream of a \$5 trillion economy is unclear at best with no clarification on the distribution of wealth and impact from throughout the workforce. It impacts gross value added and ultimately challenges the total loss in GDP which is larger than what we see now. There is no other way of putting it-- the impact is beyond anyone's imagination.

To defeat and defend this invisible enemy, COVID-19, the Indian government needs to come up with a two-fold approach which should cover a plan to reduce the fiscal deficit, creating demand and boosting the informal sector as well as providing a stimulus package directly to the overlooked informally employed population to create purchasing power.

The monetary approach being used provides some support, but a lack of initiative in fiscal policy is creating issues. Any type of support by way of fiscal policy would bring a drastic change and a minimum wage for informal workers. This needs to be rectified immediately. Only then can India fight the economic battle against COVID-19 and achieve its dreams of becoming a \$5 trillion economy.

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